

Chemical Investigation of the Bark of *Bridelia Stipularis*, Blume

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Bridelia stipularis, Blume, belonging to the Euphorbiaceae family, is distributed throughout the hotter parts of India¹. Nair and Pillai² examined the leaves of the plant and reported the isolation of a fatty alcohol, $C_{22}H_{46}O$, named as bridelyl alcohol, besides fatty acids and a phlobatanin.

We became interested to undertake a chemical investigation of the bark of *B. stipularis*, since no investigation on it was reported in literature. The bark was extracted with benzene and the neutral material from the benzene extract was chromatographed over alumina. The less polar fraction from the chromatogram was identified as the saturated triterpene ketone, friedelin (mixed m.p. and infrared), structure of which was elucidated rather recently³. The more polar fraction from the chromatogram was identified as β -sitosterol, by converting it into its acetate which was found to be identical (mixed m.p.) with β -sitosterol acetate.

Isolation of Neutral Fraction from Bridelia Stipularis.—Dried and powdered bark of *B. stipularis* (800 g.) was extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet apparatus for 6 hrs. Benzene was distilled and the dark green gummy residue was taken up in ether. The ether solution was washed with a cold 10% NaOH solution and then with water. It was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to furnish the partially crystalline neutral fraction (6.4 g.).

The above partially crystalline neutral fraction (6.4 g.) was chromatographed over a column of alumina (200 g., deactivated with 6 ml of 10% aqueous acetic acid solution). On elution with a mixture of petroleum ether-benzene (3:7), a crystalline fraction (0.23 g., m.p. 240-54°, was obtained. Further elution with benzene provided a second crystalline fraction (0.17 g.), m.p. 130-32°.

Friedelin.—The first crop of crystalline solids (0.23 g.), m.p. 240-54°, was digested with hot petroleum ether and filtered. The residue on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished a colorless, crystalline solid (0.14 g.), m.p. 262-64°, [α]_D -28° (CHCl₃), which showed negative test with tetranitromethane and was found to be identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic specimen of friedelin. (Found: C, 84.44; H, 11.90. Calc. for $C_{50}H_{50}O$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%). *Oxime*, m.p. 290-92° (lit⁴. m.p. 290-94°).

¹ Hooker, "Flora of British India", Vol V., p. 270.

² Bull. Centrl. Res. Inst., 1950, Vol. I, No. 1, Series A., 51-59.

³ Brownlie et al., J. Chem. Soc., 1956, 2419; Corey and Ursprung, J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1966, 78, 5041; Dutler et al., Helv. Chim. Acta, 1955, 38, 1268; Takahashi and Ourisson, Bull. Soc. Chim., 1956, 353.

⁴ Drake and Shrader, J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1935, 57, 1864.

β -Sitosterol Acetate.—The second solid fraction (0.17 g.), m.p. 130-32°, was acetylated in the usual manner with acetic anhydride (2 ml) and pyridine (2 ml); the acetate on crystallisation from acetone furnished *β -sitosterol acetate* (0.11 g.), m.p. 127-28°, [α]_D -41° (CHCl₃), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen. (Found: C, 81.61; H, 11.46. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₂O₂: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

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